

Associations between parents' historical experience of bullying and advice given to their child about involvement in bullying

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Parents play a pivotal role in children's bullying involvement. Parents can engage with their children regarding bullying by advising them on how to address it. Factors guiding this advice remain largely unexplored, particularly among fathers. This study aims to examine what kind of advice parents give their children regarding their involvement in bullying, and whether advice varies according to parents' role in the family and previous bullying experience. We used CHALLENGE project data (N=2,162), which targeted parents of children attending Finnish primary schools. Parents answered how likely they were to suggest ignoring, help-seeking and retaliation strategies for victims and empathy and confrontation for aggressors. Parents answered questions about their school bullying experiences. Fathers tend to suggest more ignoring and less help-seeking behaviours than mothers for victimized children. Fathers tend to be less empathetic and confrontational than mothers regarding children who bully. Parents who were aggressors in school tend to suggest more ignoring and less help-seeking behaviours. Fathers who were victimized tend to advise confronting behaviours more than mothers who were victimized, and the opposite is observed for non-victimized parents. This research highlights the need to consider parental perspectives and historical bullying experiences when examining parental influence on school bullying.